

Training of Principals as an Antecedent of Academic Performance of Students in Public Secondary Schools in Kalama Sub County, Machakos County, Kenya

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ABSTRACT: Principals of secondary schools undergo various training some organized by employer while others are organized by Ministry of education and its agencies like Kenya Education Management Institute (KEMI). These trainings come in form of INSETS, seminars, workshops and Teacher Professional Development (TPD) and are geared towards improving their leadership skills and knowledge and improve academic performance of students in schools. Despite training of principals, academic performance of students in public secondary schools have declined between 2019 to 2024. This study investigated effect of training of principals on the academic performance of students in public secondary schools in Kalama Sub County, Machakos County, Kenya. The study was guided by the goal setting theory and human capital theory. The study used mixed methodology involving descriptive survey design. The study conducted a census of all 33 principals of public secondary schools in Kalama Sub County was done. Questionnaires was used to collect data. Qualitative data was analysed using content analysis and presented in narrative form. Quantitative data was analysed using both descriptive and inferential statistics where linear regression model was utilized. The study findings indicated training of principals had significant positive effect on the academic performance of students in public secondary schools in Kalama Sub County, Machakos County, Kenya. The study recommends that school management including principals to be trained on how monitor learners' discipline and on ways of upscaling their leadership strategies in schools to improve the students' performance. There are also need ensure that field officers Quality Assurance and Standards Officers (QASOs) and Curriculum Support Officers (CSOs) are facilitated so that they may make regular school visits to offer professional support and train teachers on areas with gaps in order to improve learning in schools.

KEYWORDS: Principals, Performance Contracting, Training, Academic Performance, Public Secondary Schools.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

Training is a critical element in an organization. According to Mbua and Sarisar (2013), training has been illuminated as one of the core phases in the process of Performance Contracting (PC). The cycle of performance contracting starts with coming up with operational work plan, training for skill development, monitoring and evaluation of effectiveness of its implementations and rewarding of outstanding performance. Principals of public secondary schools in Kenya are expected to sign performance contracts with Teachers Service Commission (TSC) at the start of every year calling for need training to keep up their skills and knowledge as they execute performance contracts. Training revolves around identifying and equipping employees with skills and tacit knowledge in order to realize an organizational goal (Saira, Zafar & Hafeez, 2021). Ulla (2018) conceptualize training as valuable practices which helps employees acquire required skill and knowledge to perform certain tasks. Hitherto, Nwachukwu (2006) defined training as short-term educational process geared towards equipping employees with basic skills that are relevant for efficient performance of the tasks they are hired to perform. It organized process designed to expose employees with adequate knowledge, skills and attitude to carry out extra duties in a particular occupation, group or function in any dated field of occupation. The core reason for training is to catapult productivity, lower turnover, high morale and better coordination (Nwachukwu, 2006). Principals plays key role in improving effectiveness and equitable access to education. The role of principals is coupled with myriads of challenges, pressure, responsibilities where they are charged with duty of making strategic decisions that determine course and directions which their schools takes (Pont, 2008; Ford, Lavigne, Fiegenger & Si, 2020). Globally, there are attempts by most countries to come up with formal training package for preparation and development of school principals (Nasreen & Odhiambo, 2020). It call for need to organize for training of principals as they enter to intricate job of principals in order to be meticulous in performance

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of their duties. OECD (2008) in a study involving 22 countries noted that most principals lacked necessary education and experience to carry out their duties adequately. Wallace Foundation (2013) noted that most school principals start their careers and grow up the ladder to principals and managerial positions which might be not adequate enough for them to run the schools. Most African countries don't have official managerial training for one to become a principal where the only consideration is track record of success as teachers and that is also the case for some developed economies like Ireland, Netherland and Portugal (Bush, 2018). Review of principals training policies has prompted heterogeneous approach have been adopted which include: review of training content to capture variety of leadership knowledge, skills, and dispositions, review of entrance requirement and lastly review of the qualification requirement for one to become a principal of a school. (Vogel & Weiler, 2014; Pereda, Lucchesi, Mendes & Bresolin, 2019).

Generally, when teachers are trained, they get acquainted with repertoire of skills and knowledge which thrill learners' interest in a certain subject. This achieved as they improve their pedagogy which leads to improved academic performance and on top of that offering of solutions to educational problems (Giovazolias, Syngelaki, & Papastylianou, 2019). Saira, Zafar and Hafeez (2021) further acknowledges that when teachers are trained and skillful, they have capacity to teach and adopt varied methodologies of teaching which they apply leading to improved academic achievements of the learners. Ikram, Hameed and Imran (2020), categorize training of teacher from the training they gain as they enter teacher service (pre-service teachers) and that of experienced teachers (in-service teachers) connoting that teachers require both so that they may fit well and execute their work effectively and improve academic performance of learners in school. Junejo, Sarwar and Ahmed (2017) hitherto acknowledged training of teachers to revolves around equipping tutors with the professional skills, knowledge and experience needed to improve present and future academic performances.

Kenya Educational Management Institute (KEMI) has come up with programs to sharpen principals' management skills over time (Republic of Kenya, 2011; Kithinji, 2018). The programs are geared towards coming up with all round principals who are versed with wide range of skills and knowledge to manage dynamic issues and handling crisis in secondary schools. Alagha (2008) noted that the training updates principals' skills for improvement on performance of job-related tasks. The training of principals in Kenya takes forms like Inservice Education Trainings (INSETS) which provide short courses, seminars and workshops. School principals who have relevant high-quality management training and have undergone in-service pedagogical training are recognized for their ability to positively influence student academic performance (Sanfo, 2020). However, despite principals undertaking various trainings, the performance of most public secondary schools has dropped and students attaining entry grades to university also dropping between 2019 to 2024 in Kalama Sub County, Machakos County in Kenya (Unpublished Sub County Education Report–Kalama Sub County, 2024). The essence of training principals is to propel academic performance of students in public secondary schools which is questionable in Kalama Sub County, Machakos County which prompted need for this study.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The principals of public secondary schools have been navigating through various challenges in the management of schools they head. In order to overcome some of those challenges, principals have been undergoing training to improve on their performance of their duties and to support academic development of learners in their schools (Sanfo, 2020). However, despite principals undergoing through training like INSETs, workshops and seminars; the academic performance of students in most public secondary schools in Kalama Sub County, Machakos County has dwindled between 2019 to 2024. The number of learners attaining quality grades and transitioning to universities from public secondary schools have consistently dropped from 16.3% to 8.62% between the year 2019 to 2024. It was only 3 public secondary schools which attained a mean of 5.0 in KCSE in 2024 (Unpublished Sub County Education Report–Kalama Sub County, 2024). This indicates a paradox on whether training of principals has effect on the academic performance of students in public secondary schools in Kalama Sub County, Machakos County, Kenya. The extant empirical studies have indicated a paradox and inconclusive results with some results indicating a contradicting result. This created a gap which this study investigated.

1.3 Research Objective

To determine the effects of principal's training on the academic performance of students in public secondary schools in Kalama Sub County, Machakos County, Kenya.

1.4 Research Hypothesis

H_0 : Training of principals has no significant effect on the academic performance of students in secondary schools in Kalama Sub-County, Machakos County, Kenya.

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2.0 REVIEW LITERATURE

2.1 Theoretical Review

2.1.1 Goal Setting Theory (GST)

This study was rooted on the key assumptions of the Goal Setting Theory (GST) by Locke (1968). The theory acknowledged the prominent role played by setting goals in elevated performance of any institution. The theory accentuate that employees are committed to their work if there is goal set for them to achieve. The theory appreciate how efforts and commitments of individuals helps in achieving goals and if the individual is positive and possess requisite capacity which is gained through training makes achievement of the goal easy (Locke & Latham, 2006). At the start of every year, principals sign performance contracts with TSC which involves implementation of operational work plan and through school INSETS, workshops and seminars they are trained on how to handle the performance contracting and other issues leading to improved academic performance in schools.

Therefore, the theory sufficiently informed both independent variable (training of principals) and the dependent variable that is academic performance of secondary schools.

2.1.2 Human Capital Theory

This study was anchored on the key assumptions of the human capital theory by Schultz (1961) and which was modified by Becker (1993). They key postulate of this theory is that human being possesses skills and competences which can be optimally augmented through provision of training and professional development. Training is seen as a thriller and most critical investment which aid employees gain greater knowledge, skills and experience thus improving performance of an organization (Strober, 1990). Teachers and principals who advance their skills and knowledge end up being productive than those who are not trained (Almendarez, 2011). The theory had limitation by emphasizing on formal as compared to informal learning (Nafukho, Hairston & Brooks, 2004). However, the theory informs both independent variable (Training of principals) and academic performance of students (dependent variable of the study).

2.2 Empirical Literature

Anyanga and Kwaba (2024) conducted a study on influence of teachers' professional training and development on students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Ndhiwa Sub-County Homabay County, Kenya. The study adopted descriptive research design involving 113 teachers and 522 students in 15 public secondary schools. Data was collected using document analysis and semi structured questionnaires to collect the quantitative data, which was analyzed using descriptive statistics. The study findings indicated that teachers' professional training and development have a significant impact on students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Ndhiwa Sub-County.

Alilah and Barongo (2024) conducted a survey on the influence of training on the academic performance of public secondary school teachers in Mwanza Region, Tanzania. The training of teachers was operationalized using pre-service training, in-service training and teaching experience. The study was anchored on a behaviorism theory of learning. The study adopted descriptive survey involving quantitative research approach. The study was conducted in 22 public secondary schools which were sampled using convenient sampling involving 180 teachers. Data was collected using questionnaires and analysed using descriptive statistics and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. The study finding indicated that pre-service and in-service training influenced academic performance of learners in schools while teaching experience had negative influence academic performance of learners.

Hafeez (2021) conducted a study on impact of teacher's training on interest and academic achievements of students by multiple teaching methods in government schools in Dera Ghazi Khan, Punjab in India. The study utilized experimental research design. The study utilized multi-stage sampling to sample 80 students who were divided in to 4 groups each 20 students namely: lecture teaching method (control group), discussion teaching method (experimental method), inquiry teaching method (experimental group) and demonstration teaching method (experimental group). The instruments used for collection of data were Computer Course Achievement Test (CCAT) and computer course Interest Scale (CCIS). The results for both pre and post training were analysed to derive to descriptive statistics and ANOVA test. The study findings indicated that training of the teacher's plays an important role for choosing the best method for teaching and improved academic achievements and interests of students.

Saeed and Akbar (2021) investigated the relationship of teachers' professional skills and students' achievement in English at BA level in Punjab, India. The study was quantitative in nature and utilized correlational research design. The study population was 4th year students in session for academic ear 2014/2015 in 206-degree colleges which are affiliated to university of Punjab in the 36 districts of Punjab. The sample size was 20 percent of the colleges where 1330 students were randomly sampled. Data was collected using Students' Questionnaire for Teachers' Professional Skills (SQTPS) analysed using regression analysis. The study findings indicated a weak relationship between teacher's professional skills in assessment and student's achievements in English at BA levels.

Obiekwe and Obiekwe (2021) conducted a survey on impact of teachers training on students' academic performance in Port Harcourt Rivers State in Nigeria. The study utilized purposive sampling technique to sample 120 respondents. The Pearson Product Moment

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Correlation Co-efficient was used to test the hypothesis at significance level of 0.05 percent. The study findings indicated that significant relationship exist between teachers training and students' success in external examination and co-curricular activities.

Padillo, Manguilimotan, Capuno and Espina (2021) conducted a survey on Professional development activities and teacher performance in private non-sectarian universities in Metro Cebu, Philippines. The study was quantitative in nature and utilized descriptive survey research design. Respondents were sampled through universal sampling. Data was collected through a questionnaire where it was analysed using percentage, weighted mean and Pearson-r correlation. The results of the study indicated that professional development activities were crucial on the performance of teachers. The study had methodological gap as it utilized non-representative sampling techniques which might limit generalization of findings.

Zhaohui and Anning (2020) investigated on impact of teachers' professional development on students' academic performance in higher Education in Jiangsu University in China. The research was quantitative in nature and was a survey. The study involved 298 teachers out of 2550 faculty member who were randomly sampled. The data was collected using questionnaires and data was analysed using confirmatory factor analysis and structural equation model. The study finding indicated that PD had significant positive impact on student's academic performance in higher education.

2.3 Conceptual Framework

Literature reviewed formed basis on to which conceptual framework was developed. The conceptual framework highlighted the relation between the training of principals (Independent variable) and academic performance (Dependent variable) of learners in public secondary schools.

source: Author (2024)

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

3.0 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

According to Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2019), research design is defined as a general plan that outlines the methodology and procedure for collecting and analyzing data. This study employed descriptive survey research design. Kumar and Deshmukh (2017) recommend use of descriptive survey when collection information about certain event or population by seeking to know correct profile of people or events in order to provide wider understanding of the concept. The research design is widely applied in management related studies where this study lies (Nzomo, Kinyua and Mwasiaji, 2023). Choice of descriptive survey helped in understanding population attributes comprehensively.

3.2 Target Population

Target population is viewed as the aggregate number of people or entities which are investigated by the researcher (Creswell & Creswell, 2023). The study conducted a census of the 33 public secondary schools in Kalama Sub County, Machakos County where unit of observation was the 33 principals of those schools. Principals were involved in the study because they are in charge of schools and only people in schools who sign performance contracts where training is a component thus offering focused information on the areas of the study.

3.3 Data Collection

Questionnaire was used collect data from principals of public secondary schools in Kalama Sub County. Questionnaire has a merit as it allows respondents to give candid responses because they are anonymous. The research instruments were piloted in Machakos Sub County in Machakos County to test validity and reliability of the instruments. Face and content validity were used to test validity of the research instruments where guidance of the expert was sought. Cronbach's Alpha coefficient was used to reliability of instruments. The overall Cronbach's Alpha coefficient for the 18 items of the two variables was 0.804 which was concluded to reliable.

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3.4 Data Analysis

The study used mixed approach to analyze data where it conducted both quantitative and qualitative data analysis. Quantitative data analysis utilized both descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistics analysed and presented data using percentage, mean and standard deviation while inferential statistics utilized simple linear regression analysis model at 95% level of confidence. Qualitative data from open ended questions in the questionnaires was analysed using content analysis and presented in a narrative form as recommended by Cooper and Schindler (2014).

4 FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

The number of respondents who filled and returned questionnaires was 31 out of 33. The key informants of the study were principals of public secondary schools in Kalama Sub County, Machakos County, Kenya. This represents 93.3% of all respondents which is acceptable as recommended by Mugenda and Mugenda (2003) who propose a response rate of 70%.

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

The study utilized mean and standard deviation to clarify on the key attributes related to training of principals of public secondary schools. The analysis covered responses made by 31 respondents who filled questionnaires on the 12 items adopted to measure state of training of principals in Kalama Sub County in Machakos County, Kenya. The results of the descriptive analysis are presented in table 1.

Table 4.4: Descriptive Statistics on Training of Principals

Training of Principals	Mean	Std Dev.
In service training		
I attend in service training	4.29	.461
Inservice training has helped improve my knowledge and skills	4.48	.625
Inservice training has is linked to academic performance of students	4.55	.506
Aggregate Scores for in service training	4.44	.531
Seminars and workshop attendance		
I attend seminars and workshops in this school	4.39	.495
Seminars and workshop have improved my knowledge and skills	4.29	.643
Attendance of workshop and seminars has improved school performance	4.45	.506
Aggregate Scores for seminars and workshop attendance	4.37	.548
Professional mentorship and induction		
There are professional mentorship and induction program in school	4.32	.475
Mentorship and induction have helped improve my professionalism	4.19	.402
Professional mentorship and induction have helped improve performance of schools	4.16	.638
Aggregate Scores for professional mentorship and induction	4.22	.505
Teacher Professional Development (TPD)		
The principal has joined professional development programs	3.61	.667
Your skills have been sharpened after joining TPD	3.48	.926
TPD has improved performance of learners in school	3.62	.803
Aggregate Scores for Teacher Professional Development (TPD)	3.57	.799
Aggregate Scores for Principal's Training	4.15	.596

The results in table 1 reveal that the aggregate mean responses and standard deviation for items on training of principals in Kalama Sub County were 4.15 and 0.596 respectively. The mean score was close to 4.00 (agree) on 5-point Likert scale as adopted in this study. This means there were training of in Kalama Sub County, Machakos County, Kenya. There was agreement by most respondents that most principals had undergone training which had aided peep up their knowledge and skills and was connected to improved school's performance in Kalama Sub County. Most principals had attended workshops and seminars and which enhanced their skills and knowledge and attendance of seminars and workshops was linked to academic performance of students in public secondary schools in in Kalama Sub County, Machakos County. There was professional mentorship and inductions in the area of the study which catapulted improved professionalism among principals and improved academic performance of students in public secondary schools in Kalama Sub County. Lastly, principals have joined Teacher Professional Development (TPD) programs despite having doubt whether joining TPD had sharpened their skills. It is however noted that TPD was linked to improved academic performance of learners in public secondary schools in Kalama Sub County, Machakos County in Kenya. The study further sought

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to analyze the level of academic performance of students in public secondary school. The statistics of the academic performance of students were presented in table 2.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics on Academic Performance of Students

Academic performance in secondary schools	Mean	Std. Dev.
Students attaining quality marks in KCSE		
Most of learners attain mean grade above C+	2.35	.486
Most of learners have attained quality marks since introduction of PC for principals	2.77	.717
Aggregate Scores for Students attaining quality marks in KCSE	2.56	.602
Students attaining entry grade to university		
Most students who did their KCSE in 2023 gained entry to university	2.55	.506
The number of students attaining entry grade to university has improved after introduction of PC for principals	3.26	.773
Aggregate Scores for Students attaining entry grade to university	2.91	.426
Cases attended per term on poor academic performance		
The school cases per term related to school performance have reduced in 2023	3.35	.661
When cases related to performance reduce it leads to improved school performance	3.90	.700
Aggregate Scores for Cases attended per term on poor academic performance	3.63	.681
Aggregate Scores for Academic performance of Students in Secondary Schools	3.03	.570

The results in table 2 revealed that the aggregate mean for all responses on academic performance of learners in public secondary schools in Kalama Sub County to be 3.03 and standard deviation of 0.570. This mean is skewed towards 3.0 (not sure) on the 5-point Likert scale adopted in this study. This means that there was a doubt among respondents if the academic performance of students in public secondary schools in Kalama Sub County in Machakos County was to the expected level. Most respondents disagreed that learners attained quality grades in KCSE (C+ and above) even after introduction of performance contracting to principals. It was succinct that most learners did not attain entry grades to university and there was doubt that introduction of performance contracting have affected the state. It was further noted cases related to school performance have reduced in 2023 and this has led to improved academic performance of students in public secondary schools in Kalama Sub County, Machakos County in Kenya.

4.2 Inferential Statistics

Linear regression analysis model was adopted to test hypothesis of this study. The null hypothesis of the study was *Ho: Training of principals has no significant effect on the academic performance of students in public secondary schools in Kalama Sub County, Machakos County in Kenya.* To draw conclusions based on the inferences, the hypothesis was tested at 95% confidence level ($\alpha=0.05$). Adjusted R² was used to test how training of principals explained variation on the academic performance. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was utilized to examine whether the relationship between the study variables was significant. F statistics was computed and its corresponding P-values where the significance value was set at 0.05 where if P-value was less than 0.05, the conclusion would be that the model was significant. The coefficient of predictor values regressed against the dependent values were also evaluated. The regression analysis for training of principals and academic performance was summarized in table 3.

Table 3: Regression Results for Training of Principals and Academic Performance

Model summary					
Model	R	R square	Adjusted R ²	Standard error of estimate	
1	.638 ^a	.407	.386	.310	
ANOVA					
Model	Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Regression	1.916	1	1.916	19.894	0.000 ^a
Residual	2.793	29	.096		
Total	4.708	30			
a. Predictors: (Constant) Training of principals					
b. Dependent Variable: Academic performance of students in public secondary schools					
Model	Unstandardized coefficients		Standardized coefficient (beta)	t	Sig.
	Beta	Std error			

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Constant	0.826	.432		2.605	.0149
Training of principals	.481	.108	.638	.445	.000
Dependent Variable: <i>Academic performance of students in public secondary schools</i>					

The results in table 3 show that the Adjusted R² was 0.386. This means that training of principals (independent variables) explained 38.6 % of the changes in the dependent variable that is academic performance of students in public secondary schools in Kalama Sub County, Machakos County. The F statistics was F (1, 29) = 19.894 with a P-value of 0.000. This means that the regression model was statistically significant as the level of significance was less than 0.05 threshold. The estimated regression model for direct relation was:

$$\text{Academic Performance} = 0.826 + 0.481 \text{ Training of principals} \dots \text{Model 1}$$

The regression model indicated that holding training of principal's constant at zero, the academic performance of students in public secondary schools in Kalama Sub County was at 0.826. This means adding training of principals would enhance positively and improve the academic performance of students. The regression results confirmed that the relationship between principal's training and academic performance was statistically significant at $\beta=0.229$; $t = 0.624$; $p = 0.016$, since significance level was less than 0.05 thus rejecting null hypothesis. It was noted that unit increase in principal's training increases academic performance by 0.229 of students in secondary schools in Kalama Sub County, Machakos County, Kenya. It can therefore be concluded that there was significant positive effect of principal's training on academic performance of students in secondary schools in Kalama Sub County, Machakos County, Kenya. The results were consistent with finding by researchers like Anyanga and Kwaba (2024), Alilah and Barongo (2024), Hafeez (2021), Saeed and Akbar (2021), Padillo, Manguilimotan, Capuno and Espina (2021) and Zhaohui and Anning (2020) whose findings indicated there was a connection between teacher training and on students' academic performance in varied learning institutions.

4.3 Qualitative Analysis

The opinion of most respondents who filled open ended questions in the questionnaires revealed that most principals were involved in training. Major methods through which principals were trained included: school INSETS, workshops, seminars and undertaking TPD programs. To quote one of principals verbatim the principal noted "I participated in trainings which are organized both at school and even Sub County and County level through school INSETS, TIMEC programs, workshops and seminars. There was concurrence amongst most principals that training helps improve them skills and knowledge and training was linked to the academic performance of learners in their schools. Most principals believed that principal's training had positive effect on the academic performance of learners in public secondary schools in Kalama Sub County, Machakos County, Kenya. These qualitative results match validates results from hitherto studies by Anyanga and Kwaba (2024), Alilah and Barongo (2024) and Hafeez (2021) which indicated that principal's training had significant effect on the academic performance in learning institutions.

5.0 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

The study findings indicated that principals were trained in Kalama Sub-County in form of school INSETS, workshops and seminars. It was also realized that principal's training had significant positive effect on the academic performance of students in public secondary schools in Kalama Sub County, Machakos County, Kenya. Thus, it is with merit to conclude that training of principals had effect on the academic performance of students in public secondary schools. There is need to leverage on the best training methods for principals in order to support academic performance among learners in public secondary schools.

5.2 Policy and Practical Recommendation

This study recommends to the school management that is Board of Managements (BOMs) and school principals to be trained on how monitor learners' discipline and on ways of upscaling their leadership strategies in schools in order to improve the students' performance in schools. The study further recommends to the both TSC and MOE should ensure that Quality Assurance and Standards Officers (QASOs) and Curriculum Support Officers (CSOs) are facilitated so that they may make regular school visits to offer professional support to teacher on preparation of professional documents and on transformative pedagogical approaches to apply in order to improve learning in schools.

5.2 Limitations and Suggestions for Future Research

This study was done only in public secondary schools' level. This implies that the results cannot be generalized to other level of education thus calling for need to do the same study in other level of education like primary schools, senior schools and colleges using the same study variables and bringing in moderating variable in the study like school environment. The study also failed to capture the trend of training and its influence on academic performance over a period of time as it was a cross-sectional study. Future study should consider doing a longitudinal study for 10 years to capture such trends.

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